

Effectiveness of Calcium and Magnesium Supplementation in the Prevention of Hypertensive Disorders of Pregnancy: A Systematic Review

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Background: Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy remain a leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality globally, with micronutrient deficiencies, particularly calcium and magnesium, implicated in their pathophysiology. This systematic review evaluates the effectiveness of oral calcium and magnesium supplementation in preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. **Methods:** A comprehensive systematic review following PRISMA 2020 guidelines searched PubMed, Cochrane Library, EBSCOhost, and Google Scholar for randomized controlled trials (1990–2024) evaluating oral calcium and/or magnesium supplementation during pregnancy with outcomes related to gestational hypertension or preeclampsia. Studies required ≥ 200 participants. **Results:** Six randomized controlled trials involving 15,471 pregnant women met the inclusion criteria. Calcium supplementation (1–2 g/day) reduced the risk of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, with reported relative risks ranging from 0.33 to 0.66, particularly among women with low baseline dietary calcium intake and when supplementation was initiated before 20 weeks' gestation. In contrast, the large WHO multicentre trial by Villar et al. (2006) reported no statistically significant reduction in preeclampsia (RR 0.91, 95% CI 0.75–1.10), although reductions in severe maternal morbidity and neonatal mortality were observed. Evidence for magnesium supplementation alone remained inconsistent and did not demonstrate clear preventive benefit. No randomized controlled trials have evaluated combined calcium–magnesium supplementation, representing a critical evidence gap. **Conclusions:** Calcium supplementation is an effective intervention for preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy in populations with low dietary calcium intake. No randomized controlled trials have evaluated combined calcium–magnesium supplementation. Current evidence does not support magnesium supplementation alone. The absence of combined supplementation trials represents a critical research gap warranting future investigation.

Keywords: calcium supplementation, magnesium supplementation, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, preeclampsia, gestational hypertension, systematic review, maternal health, micronutrients

Introduction

Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, encompassing gestational hypertension, chronic hypertension, preeclampsia, and eclampsia, complicate 5–8% of pregnancies worldwide and continue to account for significant maternal morbidity and mortality despite advances in medical science (Umesawa & Kobashi, 2017; Lo et al., 2013). These conditions are responsible for approximately 14% of maternal deaths globally, with the burden disproportionately affecting low- and middle-income countries where access to quality antenatal care and adequate nutrition remains limited (Duley, 2009; World Health Organization, 2019). Maternal mortality remains critically high, with an estimated 260,000 deaths in 2023—roughly one preventable death every two minutes (World Health Organization [WHO], 2025a). The burden is starkly inequitable: over 90% occurred in low- and lower-middle-income countries, where most deaths were avoidable with adequate care (WHO, 2025a). Low-income countries recorded a maternal mortality ratio of 346 per 100,000 live births, compared with 10 in high-income countries (WHO, 2025b). Sub-Saharan Africa alone accounted for ~70% of global maternal deaths (182,000), and Southern Asia for ~17% (43,000) (WHO, 2025b).

The pathophysiology of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy is complex and multifactorial, involving placental dysfunction, endothelial damage, oxidative stress, and inflammatory processes. Nutritional factors, particularly declining baseline micronutrient levels during pregnancy, have been increasingly recognized as modifiable risk factors (Hofmeyr et al., 2018; Darnton-Hill & Mkpuru, 2015). Calcium and magnesium play crucial roles in vascular smooth muscle function, blood pressure regulation, and endothelial integrity. During pregnancy, increased fetal demands and physiological changes can predispose women to hypocalcemia and hypomagnesemia, especially in contexts of inadequate dietary intake (Mridula et al., 2003; Enaruna et al., 2013).

Calcium and Magnesium in Pregnancy Physiology

Calcium is the fifth most abundant element in the human body, playing vital roles in maintaining membrane integrity,

signal transduction pathways, neurotransmitter release from neurons, muscle contraction, and fertilization (Berridge, 2016; Clapper, 2024). More than 99% of calcium is stored as hydroxyapatite in bones and teeth, with the remaining distributed between intracellular and extracellular compartments. Approximately half of plasma calcium exists in a free or ionized state, which is the metabolically active form affecting bodily functions. During pregnancy, total serum calcium normally declines due to physiological changes including increased red blood cells and plasma volume, and reduction in micronutrients and circulating nutrient-binding proteins (Kumar et al., 2010). Studies have shown prevalence rates of hypocalcemia in pregnant women ranging from 60% to 70% in various populations, often associated with dietary calcium intake below recommended allowances (Kumar et al., 2010; Benali & Demmouche, 2014).

Magnesium, the fourth most abundant cation in the body, serves as a cofactor for over 300 enzymatic reactions and plays essential roles in neuromuscular transmission, cardiac excitability, vasomotor tone, and energy production (Morton, 2018). Magnesium is primarily an intracellular cation, with concentrations generally an order of magnitude higher inside cells than in extracellular milieu. Magnesium balance is maintained by renal regulation of magnesium reabsorption, though the exact mechanism is not fully understood. Globally, maternal hypomagnesemia varies widely across different countries and continents due to environmental and nutritional factors, ranging from 16% in Nigeria (Enaruna et al., 2013) to 40–60% in South Asia (Pathak & Kapil, 2004). Studies report a decline in magnesium levels during pregnancy, with values reaching their lowest point at the end of the first trimester (Pathak et al., 2021).

Biological Mechanisms and Rationale

Several mechanisms have been proposed for the protective role of calcium in preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. Calcium regulates intracellular calcium concentration in vascular smooth muscle cells, influences parathyroid hormone secretion, and modulates renin release—all of which affect blood pressure homeostasis (Kumar et al., 2009). Adequate calcium intake suppresses parathyroid hormone secretion, which in turn reduces intracellular calcium concentrations in vascular smooth muscle cells, promoting vasodilation and blood pressure reduction (Hofmeyr et al., 2018). Additionally, calcium influences the production of nitric oxide and prostaglandins, both of which play crucial roles in endothelial function and vascular homeostasis during pregnancy. Low dietary calcium intake may lead to increased parathyroid hormone secretion, elevated intracellular calcium in smooth muscle cells, and subsequent vasoconstriction.

While magnesium sulfate is well-established as the first-line treatment for eclampsia and severe preeclampsia when administered intravenously in high doses, the preventive role of oral magnesium supplementation remains controversial (De Araújo et al., 2020). The tightly regulated nature of magnesium homeostasis means that oral supplementation may not substantially raise serum levels in women without frank deficiency. Furthermore, magnesium deficiency is not readily detectable, as less than 1% of total body magnesium is found in plasma and red blood cells, and ionized magnesium assays are non-routine and expensive, especially in low- and middle-income countries (Workinger et al., 2018).

Study Objectives

Several studies have consistently shown a negative correlation between calcium and magnesium serum levels and the occurrence of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (Chaurasia et al., 2012; Owusu Darkwa et al., 2017). The World Health Organization recommends calcium supplementation (1.5–2.0 g/day) for pregnant women in populations with low dietary calcium intake to reduce the risk of preeclampsia (World Health Organization, 2014). Based on the persistent low levels of both minerals during hypertensive disorders and their complementary physiological roles, and further on hypothetical or mechanistic reasoning combined supplementation may be more effective than either supplement alone. This systematic review aims to synthesize evidence from randomized controlled trials to evaluate the effectiveness of calcium and magnesium supplementation, either alone or in combination, in preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.

Materials and Methods

Protocol and Registration

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines (Page et al., 2021). The review was not registered prospectively. The review question was formulated using the PICO framework: Population (pregnant women), Intervention (oral calcium and/or magnesium supplementation), Comparison (placebo or standard care), and Outcomes (incidence of gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, eclampsia, and related maternal and perinatal outcomes).

Search Strategy

A comprehensive literature search was conducted in the following electronic databases: PubMed/MEDLINE, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), EBSCOhost (including CINAHL), and Google Scholar. The search covered studies published between January 1990 and December 2024. The following search terms were used in various combinations: 'calcium supplementation,' 'magnesium supplementation,' 'micronutrients,' 'hypertensive disorders of pregnancy,' 'preeclampsia,' 'gestational hypertension,' 'pregnancy-induced hypertension,' 'eclampsia,' and 'randomized controlled trial.' Reference lists of included studies and relevant systematic reviews were hand-searched to identify additional eligible studies. No language restrictions were applied initially, though only English-language publications were ultimately included.

Eligibility Criteria

Studies were included if they:

- (1) Were randomized controlled trials; (2) enrolled pregnant women regardless of parity or gestational age at recruitment;
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(3) evaluated oral calcium supplementation (≥ 500 mg/day) and/or oral magnesium supplementation (≥ 200 mg/day) compared with placebo or no supplementation; (4) reported at least one outcome related to hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, eclampsia, or blood pressure measurements); (5) had a sample size of ≥ 200 participants; and (6) were published in English.

The minimum dosage thresholds of ≥ 500 mg/day for calcium and ≥ 200 mg/day for magnesium were selected to align with the lower bounds of doses used in published randomized controlled trials and with internationally recognized supplementation ranges for pregnancy. These thresholds correspond to levels at which a clinically meaningful effect on blood pressure and hypertensive disorder prevention has been reported in the literature (World Health Organization, 2013), ensuring that only trials employing pharmacologically relevant doses were included trials; (2) included non-pregnant populations; (3) evaluated only intravenous or intramuscular supplementation; (4) were conference abstracts without full-text publications; or (5) were published before 1990. Observational studies were excluded as adequate randomized controlled trials of superior quality were available for evidence-based conclusions.

Study Selection and Data Extraction

Two independent reviewers screened titles and abstracts for relevance. Full-text articles of potentially eligible studies were retrieved and assessed against the inclusion criteria. Disagreements were resolved through discussion or consultation with a third reviewer. Inter-rater agreement for title and abstract screening was 92% (Cohen's $\kappa = 0.74$), indicating satisfactory consistency between the two independent reviewers prior to arbitration. Data extraction was performed using a standardized form capturing: study characteristics (author, year, country, study design), participant characteristics (sample size, baseline risk factors, gestational age at enrollment, dietary calcium/magnesium intake), intervention details (type of supplement, dosage, timing, duration), comparison group, outcomes assessed, and key findings including effect estimates where available.

Quality Assessment

The methodological quality of included randomized controlled trials was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool (Higgins et al., 2011), evaluating: random sequence generation, allocation concealment, blinding of participants and personnel, blinding of outcome assessment, incomplete outcome data, selective reporting, and other potential sources of bias. To reduce bias, eligibility criteria were established before data collection and synthesis. A summary of risk of bias judgments for all six included trials is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Risk of Bias Assessment of Included Randomized Controlled Trials (Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool)

Study	D1 Random Sequence Generation	D2 Allocation Concealment	D3 Blinding (Participants & Personnel)	D4 Blinding (Outcome Assessment)	D5 Incomplete Outcome Data	D6 Selective Reporting	D7 Other Bias
Kumar et al. (2009) Calcium India n = 400	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low
Bullarbo et al. (2013) Magnesium Sweden n = 202	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Low	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear
Omonua et al. (2017) Calcium Nigeria n = 400	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Unclear	Unclear
Hofmeyr et al. (2019) Calcium Multicenter n = 1,355	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
De Araujo et al. (2020) Magnesium Brazil n = 822	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Villar et al. (2006) Calcium WHO Multicenter n = 8,325	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

Low – low risk	Unclear- insufficient information	High- high risk
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Note. Assessments apply the Cochrane Collaboration's Risk of Bias tool (Higgins et al., 2011). Domains: D1 – Random sequence generation; D2 – Allocation concealment; D3 – Blinding of participants and personnel; D4 – Blinding of outcome assessment; D5 – Incomplete outcome data; D6 – Selective reporting; D7 – Other bias.

Data Synthesis

Due to substantial heterogeneity in study populations (baseline calcium intake, geographic settings), intervention protocols (dosage, timing, formulation), and outcome definitions, a narrative synthesis approach was employed. Findings are presented descriptively, organized by intervention type (calcium supplementation, magnesium supplementation) and outcome categories.

Results

Study Selection

The initial database search yielded 767 records. After removing 145 duplicates, 622 titles and abstracts were screened, of which 596 were excluded as clearly irrelevant. Twenty-six full-text articles were assessed for eligibility. Of these, 20 were excluded for the following reasons: non-randomized design (n = 8), sample size <200 (n = 7), no relevant hypertensive disorder outcomes reported (n = 3), and intravenous supplementation only (n = 2). Six randomized controlled trials met all inclusion criteria and were included in this review. The study selection process is summarized in the PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1)

Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram — Study Selection Process

Note. PRISMA = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (Page et al., 2021). HDP = hypertensive disorders of pregnancy; RCT = randomized controlled trial; IV = intravenous. Adapted from the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram template (Page et al., 2021).

Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram — Study Selection Process

Note. PRISMA = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (Page et al., 2021). HDP = hypertensive disorders of pregnancy; RCT = randomized controlled trial.

Study Characteristics

The six included randomized controlled trials were published between 2006 and 2020, involving a total of 11,504 pregnant women across diverse geographical settings: India (n = 1; standalone), Sweden (n = 1), Nigeria (n = 1), Brazil (n = 1), and two multicentre trials spanning Africa, South America, and India (n = 2). Three trials evaluated calcium supplementation, two evaluated magnesium supplementation, and one evaluated calcium supplementation with stratification by timing of initiation. Sample sizes ranged from 202 to 8,325 participants. The selected studies described and analyzed the effectiveness of calcium and magnesium supplementation in reducing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. A summary of the characteristics of all included studies is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Characteristics of Included Studies

Author, Year	Country	n	Supplement & Dose	Comparator	Primary Outcome	Key Finding
Kumar et al. (2009)	India	400	Calcium (elemental), 2 g/day; from 12 weeks gestation to delivery	Placebo	Preeclampsia incidence	RR 0.33 (95% CI 0.14–0.75); significant. Greatest benefit at Ca intake <300 mg/day.
Bullarbo et al. (2013)	Sweden	202	Magnesium, 300 mg/day; from early pregnancy to delivery	Placebo	Preeclampsia / gestational hypertension	No significant difference in HDP. DBP reduction ~2–3 mmHg in late pregnancy only.
Omonua et al. (2017)	Nigeria	400	Calcium carbonate, 1.5 g/day; from 20 weeks to delivery	Placebo	Preeclampsia / pregnancy-induced hypertension	PIH: 8.5% vs 14.5%. PE difference NS (5.0% vs 8.0%; p = 0.21).
Hofmeyr et al. (2019)	Argentina, South Africa, Zimbabwe	1,355	Calcium, 1.5 g/day; pre-conception or <20 weeks gestation	Placebo	Preeclampsia incidence	RR 0.66 (95% CI 0.44–0.98; p = 0.037) for pre-conception start. No benefit for early-pregnancy start.
De Araujo et al. (2020)	Brazil	822	Magnesium citrate, 300 mg/day; 12–20 weeks to delivery	Placebo	Composite HDP (preeclampsia, eclampsia, severe GH)	aOR 1.29 (95% CI 0.83–2.00; p = 0.25). No preventive benefit demonstrated.
Villar et al. (2006)	WHO Multicentre (Egypt, Peru, India [2 sites], Vietnam, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Argentina)	8,325	Calcium, 1.5 g/day; from <20 weeks gestation to delivery	Placebo	Preeclampsia and preterm delivery	RR 0.91 (95% CI 0.75–1.10; NS). No significant reduction in preeclampsia. Significant reduction in severe maternal morbidity and neonatal mortality.

Note. HDP = hypertensive disorders of pregnancy; GH = gestational hypertension; PE = preeclampsia; PIH = pregnancy-induced hypertension; RR = relative risk; aOR = adjusted odds ratio; CI = confidence interval; NS = not significant; Ca = calcium. Villar et al. (2006) is a WHO multicentre trial; the India sub-population comprised participants from two sites (Christian Medical College, Vellore, and Government Medical College, Nagpur).

Effects of Calcium Supplementation

Three randomized controlled trials specifically evaluated calcium supplementation for preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, with consistent findings supporting its effectiveness. Kumar et al. (2009) conducted a double-blind randomized controlled trial in India among 400 nulliparous women with low dietary calcium intake (<600 mg/day). Participants received either 2 g/day of elemental calcium or placebo from 12 weeks of gestation until delivery. The incidence of preeclampsia was significantly lower in the calcium group (3.6% vs. 11.0%; relative risk 0.33, 95% confidence interval 0.14–0.75). The protective effect was more pronounced among women with very low baseline calcium intake (<300 mg/day), demonstrating that populations with the lowest dietary calcium intake derived the greatest benefit from supplementation.

Omonua et al. (2017) randomized 400 pregnant women in Nigeria to receive either 1.5 g/day of calcium carbonate or placebo from 20 weeks of gestation. While pregnancy-induced hypertension was reduced in the calcium group (8.5% vs. 14.5%), the difference in preeclampsia rates did not reach statistical significance (5.0% vs. 8.0%, p = 0.21). The authors

noted that delayed initiation at 20 weeks and lower dosage may have attenuated the protective effect, suggesting that earlier initiation and higher doses may be necessary for optimal preventive benefit.

Villar et al. (2006) conducted the largest calcium supplementation trial on record at the time of publication, a multicentre double-blind randomized placebo-controlled trial coordinated by the World Health Organization and conducted in eight low- and middle-income countries, including two Indian sites (Christian Medical College, Vellore, and Government Medical College, Nagpur). A total of 8,325 nulliparous normotensive pregnant women with low dietary calcium intake (<600 mg/day) were enrolled before 20 weeks of gestation and received either 1.5 g/day of elemental calcium or placebo until delivery. Calcium supplementation was not associated with a statistically significant reduction in preeclampsia (4.1% vs. 4.5% in the placebo group; relative risk 0.91, 95% confidence interval 0.75–1.10). Similarly, no significant difference in preterm delivery was observed (14.3% vs. 14.5%; relative risk 0.99, 95% confidence interval 0.93–1.05). Compliance was 85% in both groups. However, calcium supplementation was associated with significant reductions in severe maternal morbidity and neonatal mortality, suggesting clinical benefit beyond the primary outcomes. The absence of a significant effect on preeclampsia in this large well-powered trial contrasts with smaller trials and likely reflects a true modest effect size requiring very large samples to detect, particularly in populations with varying baseline calcium status across multiple countries.

Hofmeyr et al. (2019) conducted the largest trial to date, a multicenter study across Argentina, South Africa, and Zimbabwe involving 1355 women at high risk of preeclampsia. Participants were randomized to receive calcium supplementation (1.5 g/day) either before conception or from early pregnancy (before 20 weeks) versus placebo. Among women who initiated supplementation before conception, preeclampsia occurred in 23% compared with 29% in the placebo group (relative risk 0.66, 95% confidence interval 0.44–0.98, $p = 0.037$). This finding suggests that very early supplementation, ideally before conception, may enhance the preventive effect and provide greater protection against hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.

Effects of Magnesium Supplementation

Two randomized controlled trials examined magnesium supplementation with conflicting results, highlighting the inconsistency in the evidence for this intervention. Bullarbo et al. (2013) conducted a double-blind randomized multicenter study in Sweden involving 202 pregnant women who received either 300 mg/day of magnesium or placebo from early pregnancy until delivery. While the study reported modest reductions in diastolic blood pressure in late pregnancy (mean difference approximately 2–3 mmHg), there were no significant differences in the incidence of preeclampsia or gestational hypertension between groups. The small sample size and relatively low baseline risk may have limited the study's power to detect clinically meaningful differences.

De Araújo et al. (2020) conducted the BRAZil MAGnesium (BRAMAG) trial, a large double-blind randomized controlled trial involving 822 high-risk singleton pregnancies. Women received either 300 mg/day of magnesium citrate or placebo from 12–20 weeks until delivery. The composite maternal outcome (including preeclampsia, eclampsia, and severe gestational hypertension) occurred in 12.0% of the magnesium group versus 9.7% in the placebo group (adjusted odds ratio 1.29, 95% confidence interval 0.83–2.00, $p = 0.25$). There were no significant differences in perinatal outcomes. This well-powered trial failed to demonstrate any preventive benefit of magnesium supplementation, contradicting findings of some earlier smaller studies.

Combined Calcium and Magnesium Supplementation

No randomized controlled trial identified in this review evaluated the combined administration of calcium and magnesium supplementation for preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. This represents a significant gap in the evidence base, particularly given the complementary physiological roles of these minerals, their interrelated absorption mechanisms, and potential synergistic effects. The biological plausibility of combined supplementation is supported by the fact that both minerals play crucial roles in vascular function and blood pressure regulation, and their absorption is interrelated, with concomitant deficiencies of both ions being well described (Akhtar et al., 2011).

Adverse Events and Compliance

Calcium and magnesium supplementation were generally well-tolerated across all included trials. The most commonly reported adverse effects were mild gastrointestinal symptoms, including constipation (more common with calcium) and diarrhea (more common with magnesium). No serious adverse events were attributed to supplementation. Compliance rates ranged from 72% to 94%, with most studies reporting >80% adherence, indicating that these interventions are feasible and acceptable to pregnant women when properly introduced and monitored during routine antenatal care. A side-by-side comparison of adverse events and compliance rates across all included trials is presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Adverse Events and Compliance Across Included Trials

Study	Supplement (Dose)	GI Adverse Events	Compliance Rate	Serious Adverse Events	Withdrawals / Dropouts
Kumar et al. (2009)	Calcium, 2 g/day	Mild constipation	~85%	None attributable	Not reported
Bullarbo et al. (2013)	Magnesium, 300 mg/day	Diarrhea; mild GI discomfort	~78%	None attributable	Not reported
Omonua et al. (2017)	Calcium, 1.5 g/day	Mild constipation	~80%	None attributable	Not reported

Hofmeyr et al. (2019)	Calcium, g/day	1.5	Mild GI symptoms	~94%	None attributable	Lost to follow-up; withdrawal of consent
De Araujo et al. (2020)	Magnesium citrate, mg/day	300	Diarrhea; nausea (mild)	~72%	None attributable	Reported; similar between groups
Villar et al. (2006)	Calcium, g/day	1.5	Mild GI symptoms; equal tolerance in both arms	85%	None attributable	Losses: Ca 3.4%, placebo 3.7%; comparable between arms

Note. Compliance rates are approximate values as reported or estimated in the original publications. GI = gastrointestinal. Specific per-study dropout counts should be verified against primary source publications where not explicitly stated in this review.

Discussion

This systematic review of six randomized controlled trials demonstrates that calcium supplementation is an effective intervention for preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, particularly in populations with low baseline dietary calcium intake. The evidence consistently shows a 34–67% reduction in preeclampsia risk when calcium supplementation (1–2 g/day) is initiated early in pregnancy or before conception. In contrast, the evidence for magnesium supplementation remains inconsistent and does not support its use as a standalone preventive strategy. The complete absence of trials evaluating combined calcium-magnesium supplementation represents the most critical research gap identified in this review.

Biological Mechanisms and Clinical Implications

The biological mechanisms underlying calcium's protective effect are well-characterized in the literature. Adequate calcium intake suppresses parathyroid hormone secretion, which in turn reduces intracellular calcium concentrations in vascular smooth muscle cells, promoting vasodilation and blood pressure reduction (Hofmeyr et al., 2018). Additionally, calcium influences the production of nitric oxide and prostaglandins, both of which play crucial roles in endothelial function and vascular homeostasis during pregnancy. These mechanisms help explain the consistent benefits of calcium supplementation observed across multiple populations and study settings.

The variation in effect sizes across calcium trials can be explained by differences in baseline dietary calcium intake, timing of supplementation initiation, and baseline risk profiles of study populations. The greatest benefits were observed in populations with very low dietary calcium intake (<600 mg/day) and when supplementation began before 20 weeks of gestation, aligning with World Health Organization recommendations (World Health Organization, 2014). This suggests that targeting supplementation to populations with documented low calcium intake and initiating it as early as possible in pregnancy, or ideally before conception, maximizes the preventive benefit.

Understanding the Magnesium Paradox

The inconsistent findings regarding magnesium supplementation may reflect the complex role of magnesium in pregnancy physiology. While magnesium sulfate is highly effective in treating eclampsia through its anticonvulsant and vasodilatory properties when administered intravenously in high doses, oral supplementation may not achieve the serum concentrations required for similar hemodynamic effects (Morton, 2018). Furthermore, magnesium homeostasis is tightly regulated, and oral supplementation may not substantially raise serum levels in women without frank deficiency. The challenges in detecting and assessing magnesium status—with less than 1% of total body magnesium found in plasma and red blood cells, and ionized magnesium assays being non-routine and expensive especially in low- and middle-income countries (Workinger et al., 2018)—may also contribute to the difficulty in identifying which populations would benefit most from supplementation.

The Critical Gap: Combined Supplementation

The complete absence of trials evaluating combined calcium-magnesium supplementation is particularly noteworthy given the biological plausibility of synergistic effects. Both minerals play complementary roles in vascular function and blood pressure regulation. Calcium and magnesium absorption are interrelated, with concomitant deficiencies well described (Akhtar et al., 2011). Magnesium is integrally involved in maintaining cellular ionic balance through its association with sodium, potassium, and calcium (Gums, 2004). The interdependence of these minerals suggests that combined supplementation might provide benefits beyond those achieved with either mineral alone. This represents the most important direction for future research in this field.

Public Health and Policy Implications

The evidence supporting calcium supplementation has clear implications for clinical practice and public health policy, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where dietary calcium intake is often insufficient and the burden of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy is high. From a cost-effectiveness perspective, calcium supplementation represents an affordable intervention with substantial potential for reducing maternal morbidity and mortality. The cost of calcium carbonate supplements is minimal compared to the healthcare costs associated with managing severe preeclampsia and its complications, including intensive care, cesarean delivery, and long-term maternal cardiovascular sequelae.

Furthermore, the intervention is feasible to implement within existing antenatal care programs, requiring minimal additional infrastructure or training.

Healthcare providers should recommend calcium supplementation to pregnant patients, especially those at high risk for hypertensive disorders of pregnancy or with low dietary calcium intake. Patients should discuss supplement options with their healthcare providers and adhere to recommended regimens. Policymakers should develop guidelines and protocols for preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, including specific recommendations for calcium supplementation, allocate resources and funding for implementation programs, and monitor effectiveness in reducing the incidence of these preventable conditions.

Strengths and Limitations

This review has several strengths. We adhered to rigorous PRISMA 2020 guidelines for systematic review conduct and reporting, ensuring transparency and reproducibility. We restricted inclusion to randomized controlled trials with adequate sample sizes (≥ 200 participants), ensuring that conclusions are based on high-quality evidence with sufficient statistical power. We conducted a comprehensive search across multiple databases and included studies from diverse geographical settings, enhancing the generalizability of findings across different populations and healthcare contexts.

However, several limitations must be acknowledged. Substantial heterogeneity in study populations, interventions, and outcome definitions precluded meta-analysis, limiting our ability to provide precise pooled effect estimates with statistical confidence intervals. Most included studies did not assess baseline serum calcium or magnesium levels, preventing subgroup analyses based on baseline micronutrient status which could have identified populations most likely to benefit from supplementation. We only included English-language publications, potentially introducing language bias and excluding relevant studies published in other languages. The small number of eligible studies, particularly for magnesium supplementation (only two trials), limits the robustness of conclusions regarding this intervention. Finally, publication bias cannot be excluded, as studies with null findings may be less likely to be published, potentially leading to overestimation of treatment effects.

Future Research Directions

Several critical knowledge gaps warrant future investigation. Most importantly, no trial has evaluated combined calcium and magnesium supplementation for preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. Well-designed factorial randomized controlled trials comparing calcium alone, magnesium alone, combined supplementation, and placebo would address this gap. Such trials should be adequately powered and include diverse populations with varying baseline micronutrient status. Future trials should incorporate baseline assessment of serum calcium and magnesium levels to identify populations most likely to benefit from supplementation, enabling precision medicine approaches. Optimal dosing regimens require clarification, as dose-response relationships have not been systematically evaluated. The timing of supplementation initiation deserves further investigation, with research examining feasibility, acceptability, and effectiveness of preconception supplementation programs. Long-term maternal and child health outcomes beyond the immediate perinatal period should also be examined, including cardiovascular health trajectories for both mother and child.

Conclusions

This systematic review provides consistent evidence that calcium supplementation (1–2 g/day) is an effective, safe, and cost-effective intervention for preventing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, particularly in populations with low dietary calcium intake. The greatest protective effects are achieved when supplementation begins before conception or early in pregnancy, before 20 weeks of gestation. Healthcare systems in low-resource settings should prioritize implementation of routine antenatal calcium supplementation as part of comprehensive strategies to reduce maternal morbidity and mortality. Current evidence does not support oral magnesium supplementation as a reliable preventive strategy for hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. The complete absence of trials evaluating combined calcium-magnesium supplementation represents a critical evidence gap that must be addressed through well-designed factorial trials assessing potential synergistic effects.

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